

A Study on Role of Government and Financial Institutions in Entrepreneurial Development

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Dr.I.Sarumathi, Ph.D.,

Principal, Annai Women's College, Punnamchatram, Karur

Abstract

Finance plays a vital role in any kind of activities. Finance is the main source to start up a business whether it may be small or big. Finance has been an important resource to start and run an enterprise because it facilitates to procure the necessary requirements needed to commence the business such as land, labour, material, machines and so on. Therefore it may be considered to be the life blood for an enterprise. In practical sense Is it feasible to procure the required finance in time to start up the business? In recent years government has taken initiative to provide funds to needy borrowers to develop the entrepreneurship in India in terms of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprise. This article focuses to describe the essential concepts of finance, role of government in establishing the EDPs and how the Financial institutions render their service to develop the industrial growth, thereby enhance the economic development of nation.

Keywords: Finance, MSME, Government and Financial Institutions.

Introduction

Finance is one of the essential requirements of any kind of enterprise. When the entrepreneur wants to start up the business, they need to know about the type and extent of their financial requirements. Entrepreneurs start their business with the small quantum of their own capital, this may not be sufficient to establish their enterprise. Therefore it is the bounden duty that every enterprise has to chalk out its future financial requirements in its very beginning itself. The government of India as a part of its policy of promotion of small- scale sector in the country has set up of Institutions to meet the financial requirements of entrepreneur's especially small entrepreneurs.

Statement of the Problem

Financing an enterprise whether large or small is the critical element for the success of business. There are many instances to cite that many enterprises failed to explore because they were under-capitalised. Hence financial planning is much needed in order to take good decision well in advance regarding the future financial aspects of their business.

If the entrepreneur should clearly answer the following questions, he/she will be able to forecast the business plan successfully:

- What will be quantum of finance needed?
- Where to procure the needed Finance?
- When the needed finance be available?
- Proper disbursement of Finance to the entrepreneurs in time is must.

This is one of the reasons why industries have not been developing in backward areas in spite of financial assistance and concessions given by the government. Hence it necessitates studying how the entrepreneurs are able to raise their funds from government and other financial institutions to flourish their business.

Need for the Study

Entrepreneurship continues to be the important to every industrial sector. Its importance can be evaluated in terms of innovation, challenges of taking risks, creation of new starts-up and generation of employment opportunities. In India, tremendous latent entrepreneurial talent exists, if it is properly sharpens; it will help to accelerate the growth of socio-economic development and also balanced regional development can be made. Thus this paper aims to bring out the importance to study the various kinds of support and facilities provided by various institutions to the entrepreneurs to help them to establish industries.

Objectives of the Study

- To portray the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem.
- To Analyse the role of Government in promoting the EDPs
- To understand the Financial Institutions support to entrepreneurs
- To Study the role of MSME schemes.
- To Highlight the role of DIC and TCOs

I. Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

Ecosystem of the Entrepreneurial development is surrounded by various aspects such as government policy, regulatory Framework & infrastructure, Funding & Finance, Culture, Mentors, Advisors & support systems etc., which is depicted in the following diagram:

It has been observed from the above chart that the entrepreneurial development will be done in the economy when the entrepreneurs understand the concepts of ecosystem of entrepreneurs.

- i. The government has implemented numerous policy in order to help the small entrepreneurs to establish their enterprise. Thorough knowledge of the policy should be gathered by the budding entrepreneurs to start up their business.
- ii. Moreover the government has initiated proper regulatory framework through financial institutions as well as many national small scale industries.
- iii. Funding through these services institutes will be done by the government. Proper guidance can be had from the DIC and TCos in this regard.
- iv. The culture is the most important factor to determine the product to be produced in the particular district or region. Small Scale industrial Sector in a particular region should undergo the study of cultural habitual of the people who live in those regions.
- v. When we want to start up a small or large scale business, help can be sorted from the various agencies from the government side.
- vi. Now- a day's Universities acts as a catalyst to provide information to the students and encourage them to began an entrepreneur.
- vii. For this Almost in all higher education institutions and in Universities, it has been stimulated to start Entrepreneurial Cell to provide proper education and Training to the students during the period of study.
- viii. Human Capital is the important concept to produce the products and commodities. They have been given proper training to develop their skill to face the challenges to become an entrepreneur.
- ix. Finally, whatever the product produced by the new entrepreneurs, that should be marketed locally or globally. In this regard, guidance will be given the District Industrial Centres to the needy borrowers and manufactures to market their product.

II. Role of Government in Organsing EDPs

The role of Government in organising EDPs is considered significant in a country like ours. The major problem is the conversion of the surplus manpower into productive purpose ie., useful labour force to turn them into real entrepreneurs to fight with the problem of unemployment and poverty is done through the mechanism of EDPs.

The State Government and Union have undertaken to organise EDP in a sustained manner which is shown in the following diagram:

The above said institutions helps the entrepreneurs to develop their business financially and technically to foster the growth of our economy.

- National Institute for Entrepreneurship and Small Business Development
- Small Industries Service Institutes

- National Institute for Small Industry Extension and Training
- Entrepreneurship Development Institute of India
- National Science and Technology Entrepreneurship Development Board

IEDs & CEDs Specialised Institutions, Schemes which include:

- Prime Minister's Rojgar Yojana (PMRY) Scheme
- Swarnajayanti Gram Yojana (SGSY) Scheme
- Rural Employment Generation Scheme (REGP) Scheme.

III. Financial Institutions Support

Institutional Support helps to make the economic environment more conducive to business or industry. There are various kinds of support and facilities provided by the institutions to the entrepreneurs to help them to establish industries. This can be predicted in the following figure:

The above diagram depicts the financial support rendered by various institutions to develop their business. The following are the general functions performed by these institutions.

- To provide machinery on hire-purchase scheme to small scale industries.
- To procure equipment leasing facility.
- To participate in bulk purchase programme of the Government.
- To impart training in various industries trades.
- To distribute basic raw material among small scale industries through raw material depots.

IV. Role of Micro, Small, Medium Enterprise (MSME)

This is the main initiative taken by the government to develop micro, small and medium enterprise. This Scheme given lot of opportunities for new entrepreneurs for those who possess required qualification of the unemployed educated youth. The various loans schemes provided by the government can be known through the following links:

NEEDS Subsidy in Tamil Nadu

- The New Entrepreneur cum Enterprise Development Scheme (NEEDS) is a scheme promoted by the Directorate of Industries and Commerce, Government of Tamil Nadu. The objective of the scheme is to provide educated youth with opportunities for entrepreneurship by providing capital and interest subsidy. In this article, we take a brief look at the features of the NEEDS Scheme in Tamil Nadu:

NEEDS scheme eligibility criteria

- Age Criteria: All entrepreneurs within the age of 21 to 35 are eligible under the General Category. Entrepreneurs within the age of 21 to 45 who are also Women / SC / ST / BC / MBC / Minorities / Ex-Servicemen / Transgenders / Differently abled persons are eligible under the Special Category.
- Academic Qualification: The entrepreneur must hold a Degree, Diploma, ITI / Vocational Training from a recognized Institution.
- Place of Residence: The entrepreneur should be a resident of Tamil Nadu for not less than 3 years.
- Business Entity: Entrepreneurs starting their business as a proprietorship or partnership are eligible for the subsidy under the NEEDS Scheme. Also, the business should be a new business.
- Collateral Security: Collateral security will be decided as per Bank / Tamil Nadu Industrial Investment Corporation Limited (TIIC) guidelines. Loans may also be covered under Credit Guarantee Fund Trust Scheme for Micro and Small Enterprises (CGTMSE) Scheme.

Few Activities Eligible for Assistance under NEEDS Scheme were given below

- Any activity directly connected with agriculture.
- Sericulture (Cocoon rearing), Animal Husbandry like Piggery, Poultry etc.,
- Manufacturing of containers made of recycled plastic for storing, carrying, dispensing or packaging of food stuff.
- Sugar.
- Distilleries Water
- Aluminum, Iron and Steel Smelting [Excluding foundries].
- Manufacturing of intoxicant items like Beedi / Pan / Cigar / Cigarette etc.,

V. Role of Dic and TCOs

District Industrial Centres-(DICs)

- Started on May 8, 1978
- To administer the work at the district level
- To promote SSI in rural areas
- Single window interacting agency
- Registration of Small Scale is done.
- To conduct Industrial Potential surveys.
- To Guide entrepreneurs in procuring needs materials for business.

Technical Consultancy Organisations (TCOs)

- Network of TCOs was established in 70s and 80s
- In Collaboration with state-level financial institutions
- To cater the consultancy needs of small industries and new entrepreneurs
- At present 17 Tcos are functioning throughout the country.

Conclusion

It has been concluded that the government has taken various steps to promote small scale industries by providing various schemes to the new entrepreneur as well as for existing entrepreneurs to develop their business. The educated unemployed youth should approach the nearest banks/ District Industrial Centres for any kind of help needed to start up their new ventures. This is the new initiative taken by our Prime Minister in the name of PMEGP (Prime Minister Employment Generation Programme) by providing employment opportunities to all young educated to enhance their skills and to foster faster economic development of a nation.

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